

Notes on some species of *Allactoneura* De Meijere (Diptera: Mycetophilidae: Leiinae)

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Abstract: The fungus gnat genus *Allactoneura* is basically Afro-Oriental in distribution, extending into the eastern Palaearctic, New Guinea and northern Australia. New data on the distribution of *Allactoneura argentosquamosa*, *A. akasakana*, *A. cincta* and *A. formosana* are presented. *A. akasakana* is discussed as probable synonym of *A. argentosquamosa*.

Keywords: *Allactoneura*, China, distribution, Japan, Oriental Region

Introduction

Allactoneura De Meijere (type species *A. cincta* De Meijere, 1907) is a small genus currently comprising nine described extant species: *A. akasakana* Sasakawa, 2005, *A. argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), *A. cincta* De Meijere, 1907, *A. formosana* Enderlein, 1910, *A. neocaledonica* Matile, 1993, *A. nigrofemorata* De Meijere, 1913, *A. obscurata* (Walker, 1865), *A. papuensis* Bechev, 1995 and *A. ussuriensis* Zaitsev, 1981. The species *A. formosana* and *A. nigrofemorata* are synonyms of *A. cincta* according to some authors (Brunetti, 1920; Edwards, 1932; Henning, 1955; Tuomikoski, 1966; Colless & Leipa, 1973), but Zaitsev (1981) differs the three species. Two additional species are being described by Amorim et al. (preprint) from Singapore. Söli (2017) noted additional specimens from Burundi, Democratic Republic of the Congo and Tanzania with unclear systematic position. The genus has been recorded from the Afrotropical, Oriental, Australasian/Oceanian and Palaearctic Regions. We consider as doubtful the belonging of the single

described fossil species, *A. veiti* Theobald, 1937 to the genus. The aim of this contribution is to present new data on the taxonomy and distribution of some species of the genus.

Material and methods

This contribution is based on the study of type specimens of *A. argentosquamosa*, one specimen of *A. formosana* from Naturalis Biodiversity Center – Amsterdam, and three specimens of *Allactoneura* collected by Dr Ignac Sivec, Mr Jacobs and Mr Chantaramongkol from SE Asia, deposited in Regional Natural History Museum of Plovdiv – Bulgaria. Also, information from literature and web sources was analysed.

The terminalia of the studied specimens were removed and subsequently macerated in 10% warm KOH. Dissections and temporary slides were made in glycerol. The slides were photographed by digital camera Canon EOS 750D fit to the compound microscope (camera with 24×36 mm film for Fig. 6). The

terminalia were afterwards transferred to microvial with glycerine and stored together with the specimen.

Results

Genus *Allactoneura* De Meijere, 1907

Allactoneura De Meijere, 1907: 201. Type species: *Allactoneura cincta* De Meijere, by monotypy.

Scottella Enderlein, 1910: 60. Type species: *Scottella argentosquamosa* Enderlein, original designation. Synonymy: De Meijere (1913).

Allactoneura argentosquamosa (Enderlein, 1910)
(Figs 1–3)

Scottella argentosquamosa Enderlein, 1910: 61, Figs 1–2: wing. Type locality: Seychelles: Silhouette, Mahé (“Seychelen: Silhouette, Mahé”). Types: 14 ♂♂ and 37 ♀♀, National History Museum London and Museum of Zoology, Cambridge University, United Kingdom (in London, Stettin and Cambridge according to the original description).

Note. The synonymy of *Scottella argentosquamosa* with *Allactoneura cincta* De Meijere (Edwards, 1913a) is incorrect (see Edwards, 1928).

Male genitalia: Natural History Museum – London, Data Portal, #BMNHE254380; Oliveira & Amorim (2021: Figs 78–79).

Type material examined

In 1993 D. Bechev investigated the following specimens from the Zoological Museum Amsterdam (now Naturalis Biodiversity Center):

- 1 ♂: with labels: “Mahe, ’08-9., Seychelles Exp.”, “taken in coitu 13.09”, “*Scottella argentosquamosa* Enderl. Type”. The specimen was designated/labeled as: “*Allactoneura argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), Lectotype, des. D. Bechev, 1993”, but not published,
- 1 ♀: with same labels. The specimen was designated/labeled as: “*Allactoneura argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), Paralectotype, des. D. Bechev, 1993”, but not published,
- 1 ♂: with labels: “Mahe, ’08-9., Seychelles Exp.”, “*Scottella argentosquamosa* Enderl. Type, det.

Dr. Enderlein”. The specimen was designated/labeled as: “*Allactoneura argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), Paralectotype, des. D. Bechev, 1993”, but not published,

- 1 ♀: with labels: “Mahe, ’08-9., Seychelles Exp.”, “*Scottella argentosquamosa* Enderl. Type, det. Dr. Enderlein”. The specimen was designated/labeled as: “*Allactoneura argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), Paralectotype, des. D. Bechev, 1993”, but not published,
- 2 ♀: with labels: “Silhouette, ’08, Seychelles Exp.”, “*Scottella argentosquamosa* Enderl. det. Dr. Enderlein”. The specimens were designated/labeled as: “*Allactoneura argentosquamosa* (Enderlein, 1910), Paralectotype, des. D. Bechev, 1993”, but not published.

In the collection of the Natural History Museum – London (Data Portal) other type specimens are presented, too:

- lectotype (#BMNHE254380), without locality data, with photos of head, thorax, wing and male genitalia,
- 10 syntypes (#BMNH(E)254381–BMNH(E)254390) from Seychelles.

We believe that in a future revision of the type specimens it is necessary to reliably label, describe and publish lectotype and paralectotypes, selected from the types.

Other material examined: Sumatra: Fort de Kock, 920m, 1925, leg E. Jacobson, 1 ♂ (Fig. 2), in Zoological Museum Amsterdam (now Naturalis Biodiversity Center); Thailand: Chiangmai, Zoo, 400 m, 98° 57' E, 18° 48' N, 21-28.05.1988, Leg. Chantaramongkol, 1 ♂ (Fig. 3), (in Regional Natural History Museum – Plovdiv, Bulgaria).

Distribution (Fig. 7): Afrotropical region: Seychelles (Enderlein, 1910, current article), Madagascar (Stuckenberg, 1961; Oliveira & Amorim, 2021), Mauritius (Oliveira & Amorim, 2021), Diego Garcia Island (Hutson, 1981); Oriental Region: Indian Subcontinent: India: Assam (Edwards, 1928); Industan Islands: Sri Lanka (Edwards, 1928); Indo-China: Thailand (current article); Malesia: Indonesia: Sumatra (current article).

Note. Tuomikoski (1966) and Colless & Liepa (1973) noted the presence of *A. argentosquamosa* also in Tanzania (Tanganayika), Mauritius, Thailand and Malaya, but did not provide specimen information in either of the articles.

Figs 1–3. *A. argentosquamosa*, male genitalia, lateral view: 1 – BMNH Catalogue number: BMNHE254380), Type status: Lectotype; available at: <https://data.nhm.ac.uk/dataset/56e711e6-c847-4f99-915a-6894bb5c5dea/resource/05ff2255-c38a-40c9-b657-4ccb55ab2feb/record/8064230>; 2 – specimen from Sumatra: Fort de Kock, pencil drawing; 3 – specimen from Thailand: Chiangmai. Abbreviations: gc = gonocoxite; gs = gonostylus.

Allactoneura akasakana Sasakawa, 2005 (Fig. 4)

Allactoneura akasakana Sasakawa, 2005: 278. Type locality: Akasaka Imperial Garden, Tokyo, Japan. Holotype male.

Male genitalia: Sasakawa (2005: Figs 6–8), Sueyoshi et al. (2019: Fig. 3).

Note: Male genitalia are like these of *A. argentosquamosa*. Probable synonym of *A. argentosquamosa*.

Larva: Sueyoshi et al. (2019).

Distribution (Fig. 7): Palaearctic: Japan: Tokyo (Sasakawa, 2005), Honshu (Sueyoshi et al., 2019). Oriental Region: China Southeast, Zhejiang

Fig. 4. *A. akasakana*, male genitalia, lateral and dorsal view (from Sasakawa, 2005). Abbreviations: ae = aedeagus; gc = gonocoxite; gs = gonostylus.

Figs 5–6. Male genitalia, lateral view: 5 – *A. cincta*, specimen from Indonesia: N. Sumatra; 6 – *A. formosana*, specimen from Fort de Kock (Sumatra). Abbreviations: gc = gonocoxite; gs = gonostylus.

Fig. 7. Known distribution of *A. argentosquamosa* and *A. akasakana*. Legend. 1–6: *A. argentosquamosa*: 1 – Enderlein (1910), 2 – Stuckenberg (1961) and Oliveira & Amorim (2021), 3 – Oliveira & Amorim (2021), 4 – Hutson (1981), 5 – Edwards (1928), 6 – new data in current article; *A. akasakana*: orange circle – outdoor locality, yellow circle – indoor facility of shiitake mushrooms (Sueyoshi et al., 2019).

(Sueyoshi et al., 2019); Japan: Okinawa (Sueyoshi et al., 2019).

Allactoneura cincta De Meijere, 1907

Allactoneura cincta De Meijere, 1907: 202, pl. 5 Figs 2–3. Type locality: Bogor, Jawa. Holotype male.

Male and female genitalia: Zaitsev (1981, Fig. 2).

Material examined: Indonesia: N. Sumatra, W Pematang Siantar, 750 m, 23.02.1994, Leg Sivec, I., 1 ♂ (Fig. 5), (in Regional Natural History Museum – Plovdiv, Bulgaria).

Distribution: Oriental Region: Nepal (Brunetti, 1912, 1920); India (Brunetti, 1913, 1920; Senior-White, 1922; Oliveira & Amorim, 2021), Sri Lanka (Brunetti, 1912, 1920; Edwards, 1913b); Bangladesh (Brunetti, 1912, 1913, 1920; Senior-White, 1922); China Southeast: Guangdong (Hoffmann, 1938),

Taiwan (Brunetti, 1920; Senior-White, 1922); Malaysia: Sabah (Edwards, 1931, 1933); Philippines (Edwards, 1929); Indonesia: Jawa (De Meijere, 1907, 1913, 1924a, b; Brunetti, 1912, 1913, 1920; Edwards, 1928); Siberut Island (Edwards, 1932), Krakatau (Edwards, 1927; Zaitsev, 1981); Sumatra (current article).

Allactoneura formosana (Enderlein, 1910)

Scottella formosana Enderlein, 1910: 63. Type locality: “Formosa” (= Taiwan, China). Type female, probably lost.

Allactoneura formosana (Enderlein, 1910): Brunetti (1920), Zaitsev (1981).

Male genitalia: Zaitsev (1981, Figs 3.1, 3.2).

Note: *Allactoneura formosana* is included in Brunetti (1920) and subsequently in Colless & Liepa

(1973) as synonym of *A. cincta*, but Zaitsev (1981) distinguishes these species.

Material examined: 1 ♂, Fort de Kock (Sumatra), 920 m, 1925, leg E. Jacobs (Fig. 6), (in Zoological Museum Amsterdam, now Naturalis Biodiversity Center).

Discussion. Based on the examined specimen and Zaitsev's study, we consider that *A. formosana* is a valid species.

Distribution: China Southeast: Taiwan (Enderlein, 1910); Indonesia: Jawa (De Meijere, 1913; Zaitsev, 1981), Sumatra (current article).

Discussion

The male genitalia of *A. akasakana* are like those of *A. argentosquamosa* (Figs 1–4) and it is possible that the two species are identical. To clarify this question, it is necessary to compare them in detail. In the case that *A. akasakana* is a synonym of *A. argentosquamosa*, a widespread distribution of *A. argentosquamosa* (see Fig. 7) is likely due to anthropogenic spread along maritime trade routes across the Indian Ocean. The discovery of *A. akasakana* larvae in indoor facilities of the shiitake mushroom, *Lentinula edodes* (Berk.) Pegler in Japan and China (Sueyoshi et al., 2019) and the finding of *Allactoneura* sp. larvae on rotting wood (<https://dipteraandfungi.blogspot.com/search?q=Allactoneura>) is in support of this possibility.

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